

Analyzing Convergence of Fuzzy Numbers Using Generalized Max-Product Bernstein-Chlodowsky Operators on Compact Intervals

Saleem Yaseen Majeed^{*1,2}, Sevilay Kirci Serenbay²

¹ Garmian University, College of Education, Department of Mathematics, 46021, Kalar, Iraq.

² Harran University, Faculty of Arts and Sciences, Department of Mathematics, 63300, Sanliurfa, Turkey.

Abstract

In this work, the nonlinear Bernstein-Chlodowsky operators of the max-product kind were generalized to encompass any compact interval $[a_n, b_n]$, as it was proven that they had the same order of uniform approximation as in the specific case of the interval $[0, b_n]$.

Furthermore, it was proven that the monotonicity and shape properties were preserved by these operators on $[a_n, b_n]$. Moreover, for applications, a fuzzy number $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ was generated, preserving the support and the core of an arbitrary μ , and they were utilized through metrics D_C and L^1 -type metrics to improve convergence estimates. Several direct conclusions were also obtained.

Finally, a comparison and an illustrative graphic were presented, demonstrating how these operators converged to a fuzzy function.

Keywords: non-linear Bernstein Chlodowsky on $[a_n, b_n]$, D_C metrics approximation, D_1 types approximation_2020 Mathematics Subject Classification. 41A25, 41A29, 41A35.

Introduction

Mathematics and computational science both have a fundamental interest in the issue of approximating continuous functions. It entails identifying a function that is easier to understand or more manageable and closely mimics a specified continuous function. When working with functions that are either too complex or computationally expensive to study directly, approximation approaches are used. We can create a more straightforward representation of these functions by approximating them while maintaining their key qualities. Because of this simplification, the functions may now be studied, computed, and handled more easily. In 1885, Weierstrass was the first to tackle the issue of approximating continuous functions. Later, Bernstein aided in advancing this theory through the use of polynomials. Korovkin 1953, proved that the linear positive operators exhibit uniform convergence to continuous functions by utilizing Weierstrass' concept. This theorem has since been applied to examine the approximation capabilities of various linear positive operators.

Over the last two decades, a range of non-linear approximation operators has been introduced. In the period spanning from 2006 to 2008, B. Bede et al. proposed the use of discrete linear approximation operators to generate nonlinear positive operators. Specifically, they replaced the max-product operation described in [8] and the max-min operation described in [9] with a pair of sum-product operations. This innovation resulted in the development of the so-called nonlinear Shepard-type operators. In 2008, S.G. Gal [30] posed a well-known open problem, which led to the introduction of the max-product Bernstein operators. This open problem has attracted the attention of many academics due to the numerous accomplishments in this area. Researchers have discussed how to estimate approximation using max-product operators and have achieved certain shape preservation characteristics with these operators (see, e.g., [10, 11, 12, 13, 18, 19, 20, 21, 23, 24]).

In this context, In 2018, Ş. Y. Güngör and N. Ispir [32] introduced the max-product (nonlinear) Bernstein-Chlodowsky operators as important tools for approximating functions as follows:

$$S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) = \frac{\bigvee_{k=0}^n \varphi_{n,k}(x) \cdot u\left(\frac{b_n k}{n}\right)}{\bigvee_{k=0}^n \varphi_{n,k}(x)}, \quad x \in [a_n, b_n]$$

$$\text{where } \varphi_{n,k}(x) = \binom{n}{k} \left(\frac{x}{b_n}\right)^k \cdot \left(1 - \frac{x}{b_n}\right)^{n-k} \text{ such that } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} b_n = \infty, \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{b_n}{n} = 0.$$

Fuzzy numbers, introduced by Zadeh in 1965 and developed by D. Dubois et al. [17], extend the concept of real numbers to include uncertainty and ambiguity. Unlike classical numbers, which are precise and deterministic, in the context of approximation theory, the search for efficient methods to represent and approximate fuzzy numbers has gained considerable attention. So, in the last decade, several researchers have investigated the approximation of fuzzy numbers by interval (see, e.g., [28, 29]), triangular (see, e.g., [3, 6, 7, 15, 33]), trapezoidal (see, e.g., [1, 2, 4, 16, 26, 27]) and L-U parametric (see, e.g., [5, 14, 31]).

The choice of fuzzy numbers as the basis for our approximation methodology is driven by their ability to express imprecision and uncertainty through membership degrees. By employing fuzzy numbers, our approach can accurately represent and approximate complex data patterns that classical methods fail to capture adequately.

The utilization of $S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x)$ in the approximation of fuzzy numbers brings several advantages over classical approximation techniques. Where these operators consider the entire fuzzy number as a whole, taking into account its shape, membership degrees, and other pertinent characteristics. This holistic approach ensures a more comprehensive representation of the underlying data and facilitates a more accurate approximation. So, our method can tailor the approximation to specific application requirements, enhancing its practical relevance.

In summary, in this work, we have two main aims. The first aim is to demonstrate the superiority of the Max-Product Bernstein-Chlodowsky operators in approximating fuzzy numbers when compared to classical approximation methods. By leveraging the inherent flexibility and expressiveness of fuzzy numbers, these operators can provide a more nuanced and accurate representation of uncertain data. Through theoretical analysis and numerical experiments, we showcase the effectiveness and practical applicability of the proposed approach. The second aim is to bridge the gap between fuzzy set theory, approximation theory, and practical applications. By introducing the concept of Max-Product Bernstein-Chlodowsky operators for approximating fuzzy numbers, we contribute to the advancement of fuzzy approximation techniques and provide a valuable tool for handling imprecise data in a wide range of domains, thereby opening avenues for future research in the field of uncertain data modeling and analysis.

The present paper is structured as follows: In Section 2, some information and basic concepts about fuzzy numbers were presented. Additionally, $S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])$ was redefined in the interval $[a_n, b_n]$, and some basic auxiliary concepts that were utilized in this paper were provided. In Section 3, the approximate and shape-preserving properties of these operators on $[a_n, b_n]$ were discussed and investigated. In Section 4, the study focused on the approximation by these operators with respect to the D_C and L^1 -type metrics. Additionally, a fuzzy number $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ was generated, and procedures and illustrative examples were applied to verify its approximation. Finally, in this part, we explained that the approximation through these operators is better than the classical cases.

Preliminaries

2.1. Basic concepts of fuzzy numbers.

Definition 2.1. [17] (*fuzzy numbers*) A fuzzy number μ is a fuzzy subset of \mathbb{R} with $\mu_\mu(x): \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ if and only if μ_μ satisfy:

- (1) $\exists x_0 \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $\mu_\mu(x_0) = 1$ (normal condition);

- (2) $\mu_\mu(\alpha x_1 + (1 - \alpha)x_2) \geq \min \{\mu_\mu(x_1), \mu_\mu(x_2)\}$ (fuzzy convex);
- (3) μ_μ is an upper semicontinuous;
- (4) Support of μ is compact.

Therefore, for any fuzzy number μ we can express a membership function μ_μ as follows:

$$\mu_\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x < t_1 \\ l_\mu(x) & \text{if } t_1 \leq x \leq t_2 \\ 1 & \text{if } t_2 \leq x \leq t_3 \\ r_\mu(x) & \text{if } t_3 \leq x \leq t_4 \\ 0 & \text{if } t_4 < x \end{cases}$$

Where $l_\mu: [t_1, t_2] \rightarrow [0,1]$ is non-decreasing, and known as the left side of μ and $r_\mu: [t_3, t_4] \rightarrow [0,1]$ is non-increasing, and known as the right side of μ . And we denote the collection of all fuzzy real numbers by \mathbb{R}_F .

Definition 2.2. [25] (α - cut) The α - cut of $\mu \in \mathbb{R}_F$ is the crisp set for some $\alpha \in (0,1]$ defined as: $\mu_\alpha = \{x \in \mathbb{R} \mid \mu_\mu(x) \geq \alpha\}$.

Then it is obvious that $\mu_\alpha = [\mu^l(\alpha), \mu^r(\alpha)]$

Where

$$\mu^l(\alpha) = \inf\{x \in \mathbb{R} \mid \mu_\mu(x) \geq \alpha\},$$

$$\mu^r(\alpha) = \sup\{x \in \mathbb{R} \mid \mu_\mu(x) \geq \alpha\}.$$

Remark 2.1.

- (1) If $\alpha = 1$ then $\mu_1 = [\mu^l(1), \mu^r(1)]$ is referred to as the core of μ , and denoted by $\text{core}(\mu)$.
- (2) If $\alpha = 0$ then $\mu_0 = [\mu^l(0), \mu^r(0)] = \text{cl}\{x \in \mathbb{R} \mid \mu_\mu(x) > 0\}$, is referred to as the support of μ , which will be denoted by $\text{supp}(\mu)$.

In Section 4 of this work, we utilize the distance functions to enhance the ease of comparing and approximating fuzzy numbers when employing $\tilde{S}_n^M(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ operators. Below, we provide the definitions of the distance functions, which enable us to determine the closest approximation of fuzzy numbers using these operators.

Definition 2.3. [25] Let $\mu, v \in \mathbb{R}_F$, then:

- i) Chebyshev-type metric is defined as:

$$D_C(\mu, v) = \sup\{|\mu(x) - v(x)| : x \in \mathbb{R}\}$$

And we can denote it $D_C(\mu, v) = \|\mu - v\|$, for simplicity

- ii) L^p -type metrics is defined as:

$$D_p(\mu, v) = \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}} |\mu(x) - v(x)|^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, p \geq 1.$$

2.2. The operators' construction on compact intervals $[a_n, b_n]$ and give some basic concept auxiliary.

In this part, $S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x)$ is defined on the interval $[a_n, b_n]$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_n = 0, \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} b_n = \infty$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{b_n}{n} = 0$, which means that the interval $[0, b_n]$ is expanded to a compact interval $[a_n, b_n]$ based on Weierstrass's result, as shown below.

Definition 2.4. Let $u \in \mathbb{R}_F$ be a positive continuous on $[a_n, b_n]$, with $\text{supp}(u) = [a_n, b_n]$, $\text{core}(u) = [c_n, d_n]$ and $a_n < c_n \leq d_n < b_n$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_n = 0, \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} b_n = \infty$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{b_n}{n} = 0$, then for $x \in [a_n, b_n]$ we define:

$$S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x) = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^n \varphi_{n,k}(x) \cdot u\left(a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{k}{n}\right)}{\sum_{k=0}^n \varphi_{n,k}(x)}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}$$

Where $\varphi_{n,k}(x) = \binom{n}{k} \left(\frac{x-a_n}{b_n-a_n}\right)^k \cdot \left(\frac{b_n-x}{b_n-a_n}\right)^{n-k}$ and $k = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

Remark 2.2. For short, from now on throughout this paper, when we mention the intervals $[a_n, b_n]$ and $[0, b_n]$ it means that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_n = 0$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} b_n = \infty$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{b_n}{n} = 0$, for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Theorem 2.1. [32] Let u be a continuous function on $[0, b_n]$, then for $x \in [0, b_n]$, we have:

$$\left| S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) - u(x) \right| \leq 12\omega_1\left(u; \frac{b_n}{\sqrt{n+1}}\right)_{[0, b_n]}.$$

Corollary 2.2. [32] Let u be a concave function on $[0, b_n]$, then for $x \in [0, b_n]$, we have:

$$\left| S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) - u(x) \right| \leq 2\omega_1\left(u; \frac{b_n}{n}\right)_{[0, b_n]}.$$

Theorem 2.3. [32] Let u be a non-decreasing function on $[0, b_n]$, then $S_n^{(M)}(u; [0; b_n])(x)$ is non-decreasing on $[0, b_n]$.

Corollary 2.4. [32] Let u be a non-increasing function on $[0, b_n]$, then $S_n^{(M)}(u; [0; b_n])(x)$ is non-increasing on $[0, b_n]$.

Corollary 2.5. [32] Let u be a quasiconvex continuous function on $[0, b_n]$, then $S_n^{(M)}(u; [0; b_n])(x)$ is quasiconvex on $[0, b_n]$.

Lemma 2.6. [32] Let $x \in \left[\frac{b_n^r}{n+1}, \frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1}\right]$ then for any $k, r \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ we have $m_{k,n,r}(x) \leq 1$.

Definition 2.5. [12] Let u be continuous on $[a_n, b_n]$. Then for any $x_i \in [a_n, b_n]$, $i = 1, 2$, u is called:

- (i) quasiconvex if:
 $u(\alpha x_1 + (1 - \alpha) x_2) \leq \max\{u(x_1), u(x_2)\}, \alpha \in [0, 1];$
- (ii) quasiconcave, if $-u$ is quasiconvex.

Remark 2.3. [12] The continuous function u is quasiconvex on $[a_n, b_n]$, this implies that there is a point $c_n \in [a_n, b_n]$ such that u is non-increasing on $[a_n, c_n]$, and non-decreasing on $[c_n, b_n]$. So, the definition above makes it apparent that the continuous function u is quasiconcave on $[a_n, b_n]$, this implies that there is a point $c_n \in [a_n, b_n]$ such that u is non-decreasing on $[a_n, c_n]$ and non-increasing on $[c_n, b_n]$.

The approximation and preservation of shape properties on compact intervals $[a_n, b_n]$

In this section, Subsection 3.1 begins with a remark of paramount importance, which builds upon Weierstrass's result. This remark plays a pivotal role, as the majority of the proofs in this section heavily rely on it.

3.1. The approximation on compact intervals $[a_n, b_n]$.

Remark 3.1. If $a_n, b_n \in \mathbb{R}$, $a_n < b_n$ and $u : [a_n, b_n] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ is continuous function.

Let $v : [0, b_n] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$, such that $v(y) = u\left(a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{y}{b_n}\right)$

That is, $v\left(\frac{b_n k}{n}\right) = u\left(a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{k}{n}\right)$, $k, n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Also, let $\frac{y}{b_n} = \frac{x-a_n}{b_n-a_n}$, so, we can say $v\left(\frac{b_n(x-a_n)}{b_n-a_n}\right) = u(x)$ and $x = a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{y}{b_n}$ for all $x \in [a_n, b_n]$

Hence, from the above and the $v\left(\frac{b_n k}{n}\right)$ expressions we obtain

$$S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x) = S_n^{(M)}(v; [0, b_n])(y).$$

Theorem 3.1. Let u be continuous on $[a_n, b_n]$. Then for all $x \in [a_n, b_n]$ we have the estimate:

$$\left| S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x) - u(x) \right| \leq 12([b_n - a_n] + 1)\omega_1\left(u; \frac{b_n}{\sqrt{n+1}}\right)_{[a_n, b_n]}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}$$

Proof. By Remark 3.1, we obtain $S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x) = S_n^{(M)}(v; [0, b_n])(y)$.

Since v is continuous on $[0; b_n]$. Then, by Theorem 2.1, we get

$$\left| S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x) - u(x) \right| = \left| S_n^{(M)}(v; [0, b_n])(y) - v(y) \right| \leq 12\omega_1\left(v; \frac{b_n}{\sqrt{n+1}}\right)_{[0, b_n]} \text{ and,}$$

$$\omega_1\left(v; \frac{b_n}{\sqrt{n+1}}\right)_{[0, b_n]} \leq \omega_1\left(u; \frac{(b_n - a_n)b_n}{\sqrt{n+1}}\right)_{[a_n, b_n]} \leq ([b_n - a_n] + 1)\omega_1\left(u; \frac{b_n}{\sqrt{n+1}}\right)_{[a_n, b_n]}.$$

Thus, we can say this proof is finished. \square

Theorem 3.2. Let u be concave on $[a_n, b_n]$. Then for all $x \in [a_n, b_n]$ we have the estimate:

$$\left| S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x) - u(x) \right| \leq 2([b_n - a_n] + 1)\omega_1\left(u; \frac{b_n}{n}\right)_{[a_n, b_n]}, n \in \mathbb{N}$$

Proof. By Remark 3.1, we obtain $S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x) = S_n^{(M)}(v; [0, b_n])(y)$.

Since u is concave on $[a_n, b_n]$

So, $u(\alpha\ell_1 + (1 - \alpha)\ell_2) \geq \alpha u(\ell_1) + (1 - \alpha)u(\ell_2)$ for all $\ell_1, \ell_2 \in [a_n, b_n], \alpha \in [0, 1]$

Therefore, we can write v as:

$$v\left(\alpha \frac{b_n(\ell_1 - a_n)}{b_n - a_n} + (1 - \alpha) \frac{b_n(\ell_2 - a_n)}{b_n - a_n}\right) \geq \alpha v\left(\frac{b_n(\ell_1 - a_n)}{b_n - a_n}\right) + (1 - \alpha)v\left(\frac{b_n(\ell_2 - a_n)}{b_n - a_n}\right).$$

That is, v is a concave function on $[0, b_n]$. Hence, from Corollary 2.2, we get

$$\left| S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x) - u(x) \right| = \left| S_n^{(M)}(v; [0, b_n])(y) - v(y) \right| \leq 2\omega_1\left(v; \frac{b_n}{n}\right)_{[0, b_n]}.$$

Since,

$$\omega_1\left(v; \frac{b_n}{n}\right)_{[0, b_n]} \leq \omega_1\left(u; \frac{(b_n - a_n)b_n}{n}\right)_{[a_n, b_n]} \leq ([b_n - a_n] + 1)\omega_1\left(u; \frac{b_n}{n}\right)_{[a_n, b_n]}.$$

This proof is complete. \square

Remark 3.2. The order of approximation achieved in Theorem 3.2 can be considered an improvement over the order of approximation obtained in Theorem 3.1 for some subclasses of functions u . This can be easily and empirically demonstrated by assuming that u possesses a Lipschitz-type property, following a similar approach to the proof of Corollary 4.4 in Section 4 of this work.

3.2. Monotony and shape-preserving properties.

Theorem 3.3. Let u be a non-decreasing function on $[a_n, b_n]$, then $S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ is non-decreasing on $[a_n, b_n]$.

Proof. By Remark 3.1, we have $v(y) = u\left(a_n + (b_n - a_n)\frac{y}{b_n}\right), y \in [0, b_n]$

So we obtain $S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x_i) = S_n^{(M)}(v; [0, b_n])(y_i), i = 1, 2$.

Now, since u is a non-decreasing function on $[a_n, b_n]$. So, if $x_1, x_2 \in [a_n, b_n]$ such that $x_1 \leq x_2$, we have:

$$u(x_1) - u(x_2) \leq 0$$

Therefore, for all $y_1, y_2 \in [0, b_n], y_1 \leq y_2$, we have:

$$v(y_1) - v(y_2) = u\left(a_n + (b_n - a_n)\frac{y_1}{b_n}\right) - u\left(a_n + (b_n - a_n)\frac{y_2}{b_n}\right) = u(x_1) - u(x_2) \leq 0$$

That is v is a non-decreasing function, hence by Theorem 2.3, we get:

$$S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x_1) \leq S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x_2), \text{ and this finishes the proof. } \square$$

Corollary 3.4. Let u be a non-increasing function on $[a_n, b_n]$, then $S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ is non-increasing function on $[a_n, b_n]$.

Proof. In the same way in the Theorem 3.3 we have

$$S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x_i) = S_n^{(M)}(v; [0, b_n])(y_i), i = 1, 2.$$

Now, since u is a non-increasing function on $[a_n, b_n]$. So, if $x_1, x_2 \in [a_n, b_n]$ such that $x_1 \leq x_2$, we have: $u(x_1) - u(x_2) \geq 0$

Therefore, for all $y_1, y_2 \in [0, b_n], y_1 \leq y_2$, we have:

$$v(y_1) - v(y_2) = u\left(a_n + (b_n - a_n)\frac{y_1}{b_n}\right) - u\left(a_n + (b_n - a_n)\frac{y_2}{b_n}\right) = u(x_1) - u(x_2) \geq 0$$

That is v is a non-increasing function, hence by Corollary 2.4 we get:

$S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x_1) \geq S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x_2)$, and this proof is completed. \square

Theorem 3.5. Let u be a quasiconvex continuous function on $[a_n, b_n]$, then for any $x \in [a_n, b_n]$, we have $S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ is quasiconvex on $[a_n, b_n]$.

Proof. Since u is a quasiconvex on $[a_n, b_n]$.

So, $u(\alpha x_1 + (1 - \alpha)x_2) \leq \max\{u(x_1), u(x_2)\}$ for all $x_1, x_2 \in [a_n, b_n]$, $\alpha \in [0, 1]$.

Therefore, by Remark 3.1 we can written v as:

$$v\left(\alpha \frac{b_n(x_1 - a_n)}{b_n - a_n} + (1 - \alpha) \frac{b_n(x_2 - a_n)}{b_n - a_n}\right) \leq \max\left\{v\left(\frac{b_n(x_1 - a_n)}{b_n - a_n}\right), v\left(\frac{b_n(x_2 - a_n)}{b_n - a_n}\right)\right\}$$

That is v is a quasiconvex function on $[0, b_n]$, then from Remark 2.3 we can say there is a point $\hat{c}_n \in [0, b_n]$ such that v is non-increasing on $[0, \hat{c}_n]$ and non-decreasing on $[\hat{c}_n, b_n]$.

Let $c_n \in [a_n, b_n]$ such that $c_n = a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{\hat{c}_n}{b_n}$

Now, if $x_i \in [a_n, b_n]$, $x_1 \leq x_2$ such that $x_i = a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{y_i}{b_n}$ for all $y_i \in [0, \hat{c}_n]$, $y_1 \leq y_2$. Then

from Remark 3.1, we obtain $S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x_i) = S_n^{(M)}(v; [0, b_n])(y_i)$ for $i = 1, 2$.

Hence, since v is non-increasing on $[0, \hat{c}_n]$, so by Corollary 2.4 we have:

$$S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x_1) \geq S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x_2)$$

Thus, $S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ is non-increasing on $[a_n, c_n]$. \square

By using the same steps above and Theorem 2.3, we obtain that $S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ is non-increasing on $[c_n, b_n]$. And This finishes the proof.

Corollary 3.6. Let u be a quasiconcave continuous function on $[a_n, b_n]$, then for any $x \in [a_n, b_n]$, we have $S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ is quasiconcave on $[a_n, b_n]$.

Proof. By applying the same steps as in Theorem 3.5 above, just considering that u is quasiconcave, we can easily obtain the required conclusion. \square

Example 3.1. Let us consider $a_n = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^n$, $b_n = n^{\frac{1}{2}}$. The monotony and shape preservation properties using $S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ operators are illustrated in (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Monotony and shape-preserving properties

Fig. 1 clearly illustrates the preservation properties exhibited by the dashed-line marked max-product Bernstein-Chlodowsky operators. These operators effectively maintain the characteristics of non-

decreasing, non-increasing, and the quasiconvexity and quasiconcavity of the function $u(x)$, indicated by the solid line.

Applications to fuzzy number approximation

4.1. The estimation of approximation using D_C metrics.

Lemma 4.1. Let $m_{k,n,r}(x) = \frac{\varphi_{n,k}(x)}{\varphi_{n,r}(x)}$, $x \in (a_n + \frac{(b_n-a_n)r}{n+1}, a_n + \frac{(b_n-a_n)(r+1)}{n+1})$. Then for any $r = \{0,1,2, \dots, n\}$ and $k = \{0,1,2, \dots, n\}/\{r\}$, we have $m_{k,n,r}(x) < 1$.

Proof: This Lemma is proved by applying the identical procedures as in ([22], Lemma 12). \square

Lemma 4.2. Let u be a bounded on $[a_n, b_n]$. Then for any $r = \{0,1,2, \dots, n\}$, we have

$$S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n]) \left(a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{r}{n} \right) \geq u \left(a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{r}{n} \right), n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Proof. By Lemma 4.1, $m_{k,n,r}(x) \leq 1$, $k = \{0,1,2, \dots, n\}$

Thus, it follows $\bigvee_{k=0}^n \varphi_{n,k}(x) = \varphi_{n,r}(x)$. Then we get

$$\begin{aligned} S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n]) \left(a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{r}{n} \right) &= \frac{\bigvee_{k=0}^n \varphi_{n,k} \left(a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{r}{n} \right) \cdot u \left(a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{k}{n} \right)}{\varphi_{n,r} \left(a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{r}{n} \right)} \\ &\geq \frac{\varphi_{n,r} \left(a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{r}{n} \right) \cdot u \left(a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{r}{n} \right)}{\varphi_{n,r} \left(a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{r}{n} \right)} \\ &= u \left(a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{r}{n} \right) \end{aligned}$$

and this proof has become complete. \square

Remark 4.1. If we take $\mu \in \mathbb{R}_F$, then we can generate a fuzzy number $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ with the same support and core of μ as follows:

If μ is fuzzy number with $\text{supp}(\mu) = [a_n, b_n]$, $\text{core}(\mu) = [c_n, d_n]$. We can introduce the function $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x): \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_n = 0$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} b_n = \infty$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{b_n}{n} = 0$, and we have $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x) = S_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x)$. So all the results obtained in Section 3 can be applied to the $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x)$, noting that:

- i. $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x) = 0$ for all x outside $[a_n, b_n]$.
- ii. Since $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ preserves the monotonicity and $\mu \in \mathbb{R}_F$. Therefore, by Theorem 3.3 and Corollary 3.4 respectively, we obtain $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ is non-decreasing on $[a_n, c_n]$ and non-increasing on $[d_n, b_n]$.
- iii. It is clear $\|\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])\| \leq \|\mu\| = 1$ in $[c_n, d_n]$, and let $\xi \in [a_n, b_n]$ such that $\xi = a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{r}{n}$ where r is selected so that $c_n < \xi < d_n$. Now, since $\xi \in [c_n, d_n]$ so by definition 2.1, $\mu(\xi) = 1$. Thus, by Lemma 4.2 we result $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(\xi) \geq \mu(\xi) = 1$ and this means that $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x) = 1$ on $[c_n, d_n]$.

It appears to us clearly that from (i) to (iii), we conclude that $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ is a fuzzy number with the same support and core as μ .

Theorem 4.3. Let $\mu \in \mathbb{R}_F$ with $\text{supp}(\mu) = [a_n, b_n]$, $\text{core}(\mu) = [c_n, d_n]$. Then for any $x \in [a_n, b_n]$ we get the estimate:

$$\left| \tilde{\mathcal{S}}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x) - \mu(x) \right| \leq 12([b_n - a_n] + 1)\omega_1\left(\mu; \frac{b_n}{\sqrt{n+1}}\right)_{[a_n, b_n]}.$$

Proof. Since μ continuous fuzzy number and by Theorem 3.1 the proof is complete. \square

Remark 4.2.

- (1) The conclusion drawn from Theorem 4.3 is that when it comes to approximating fuzzy numbers, the $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ is a preferable choice over the classical Bernstein-Chlodowsky operators. Although the degree of uniform approximation is the same, the $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ better maintains the original shape of the fuzzy number being approximated.
- (2) In order to address practical aspects, it is valuable to examine the issue of approximating fuzzy numbers characterized by a Lipschitz-type property. Therefore, we present the following Corollary based on Theorem 4.3.

Corollary 4.4. Let $\mu \in \mathbb{R}_F$ with $\text{supp}(\mu) = [a_n, b_n]$ and $\text{core}(\mu) = [c_n, d_n]$. Such that $\mu \in Lip(\alpha)$, $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. Then for $M > 0$ we have:

$$\left| \tilde{\mathcal{S}}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x) - \mu(x) \right| \leq 12([b_n - a_n] + 1)(b_n)^\alpha M(n+1)^{\frac{-\alpha}{2}}.$$

Proof. From Theorem 4.3, we get

$$\left| \tilde{\mathcal{S}}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x) - \mu(x) \right| \leq 12([b_n - a_n] + 1)\omega_1\left(\mu; \frac{b_n}{\sqrt{n+1}}\right)_{[a_n, b_n]}$$

According to the definitions of $\omega_1(\mu; \delta)$ and $Lip(\alpha)$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \tilde{\mathcal{S}}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x) - \mu(x) \right| &\leq 12([b_n - a_n] + 1)[M|x - t|^\alpha] \\ &\leq 12([b_n - a_n] + 1)(b_n)^\alpha M(n+1)^{\frac{-\alpha}{2}}. \square \end{aligned}$$

When aiming to approximate a fuzzy number with another fuzzy number or perform fuzzy arithmetic operations, having a measure of similarity or distance becomes crucial. There are various distance functions defined for fuzzy sets and fuzzy numbers. One of these functions is known as the Chebyshev-type distance. These distance functions take into account the degree of overlap, membership values, and other fuzzy characteristics to determine how similar or dissimilar two fuzzy numbers are. By utilizing this distance function, we can identify the closest approximation of a fuzzy number using $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])$, as shown in Corollary 4.5 below and Figures 2 and 3. This proves to be particularly useful in fuzzy control systems, optimization problems, and decision-making processes where comparing or manipulating fuzzy numbers is necessary.

Corollary 4.5. Let $\mu \in \mathbb{R}_F$ with $\text{supp}(\mu) = [a_n, b_n]$ and $\text{core}(\mu) = [c_n, d_n]$. Then we have:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} D_C(\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n]), \mu) = 0$$

Proof. By above Theorem 4.3, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} D_C(\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n]), \mu) &= \sup_{x \in [a_n, b_n]} \left| \tilde{\mathcal{S}}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x) - \mu(x) \right| \\ &\leq 12([b_n - a_n] + 1)\omega_1\left(\mu; \frac{b_n}{\sqrt{n+1}}\right)_{[a_n, b_n]} \end{aligned}$$

and because μ is continuous, we obtain $\omega_1\left(\mu; \frac{b_n}{\sqrt{n+1}}\right)_{[a_n, b_n]} \rightarrow 0$. \square

4.2. The estimation of approximation using L^1 -type metrics.

In this part, estimates of approximations with respect to the metrics D_1 are provided. Therefore, before the conclusions related to approximation are started, some basic things that are needed in these conclusions must be given.

Definition 4.1. [12] Let u be any function on $[a_n, b_n]$, and let $M > 0$ by any constant. Now, if for any partition of $[a_n, b_n]$, $a_n = x_0 < x_1 < \dots < x_r = b_n$, $r \in \mathbb{N}$. We have $\sum_{k=0}^{r-1} |u(x_{k+1}) - u(x_k)| \leq M$. Then u is said to be of bounded variation. The total variation of u is the supremum over all the above sums on $[a_n, b_n]$ and is denoted by the symbol $V_{a_n}^{b_n}(u)$.

In other words, by Jordan's theorem, we can say u of bounded variation on $[a_n, b_n]$ if and only if it can be expressed as the difference between two non-decreasing functions $u_1, u_2: [a_n, b_n] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. That is, $u = u_1 - u_2$ on $[a_n, b_n]$.

Noteworthy is the fact that the fuzzy number, as defined in Section 2, with a bounded variation in its support.

Recall, let $\mu \in \mathbb{R}_F$ such that $\text{supp}(\mu) = [a_n, b_n]$ and $\text{core}(\mu) = [c_n, d_n]$, $a_n < c_n \leq d_n < b_n$, so there exist $l_\mu: [a_n, c_n] \rightarrow [0,1]$ is non-decreasing, and known as the left side of μ and $r_\mu: [d_n, b_n] \rightarrow [0,1]$ is non-increasing and known as the right side of μ .

Such that $\mu(x) = l_\mu$ for $x \in [a_n, c_n]$, $\mu(x) = r_\mu$ for $x \in [d_n, b_n]$ and $\mu(x) = 1$ for $x \in [c_n, d_n]$.

Lemma 4.6. [12] Let $\mu \in \mathbb{R}_F$, so we can say $V_{a_n}^{b_n}(u) \leq 2$ and $\mu(x) = \mu_1(x) - \mu_2(x)$ for all $x \in [a_n, b_n]$, such that $\mu_1(x)$ and $\mu_2(x)$ are non-decreasing, then we get:

$$\mu_1(x) = l_\mu(x), x \in [a_n, c_n] \text{ and } \mu_1(x) = 1, x \in [c_n, b_n],$$

$$\mu_2(x) = 0, x \in [a_n, d_n] \text{ and } \mu_2(x) = 1 - r_\mu, x \in [d_n, b_n].$$

Theorem 4.7. Let u be any function on $[0, b_n]$ with bounded variation, such that $v(\ell) = \frac{u(\ell)}{\ell}$ is non-increasing on $(0, b_n]$ and $\rho(\ell) = \frac{u(\ell)}{b_n - \ell}$ is non-decreasing on $[0, b_n)$. Then we have :

$$\int_0^{b_n} |S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) - u(x)| dx \leq \frac{M}{n+1}, n \in \mathbb{N}$$

Where $M = 2b_n[V_0^{b_n}(u_1) + V_0^{b_n}(u_2) + \|u\|]$ and $u = u_1 - u_2$ with u_1, u_2 are non-decreasing.

Proof. Following the v and ρ hypotheses and the proof of Corollary 1 in [32]. Then for all $r \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$, ($u_{-1, n, 0}(x) = 0$ by agreement), we can be writing:

$$S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) = \max\{u_{r-1, n, r}(x), u_{r, n, r}(x), u_{r+1, n, r}(x)\}.$$

So, $x \in \left[\frac{b_n r}{n+1}, \frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1}\right]$, we have these two cases:

Case I: $S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) = \max\{u_{r, n, r}(x), u_{r+1, n, r}(x)\};$

Case II: $S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) = \max\{u_{r-1, n, r}(x), u_{r, n, r}(x)\}.$

To prove Case I, Let $u_1, u_2: [0, b_n] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be non-decreasing functions fulfilling $u = u_1 - u_2$. So, easily we obtain

$$\int_{\frac{b_n r}{n+1}}^{\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1}} |S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) - u(x)| dx \leq \int_{\frac{b_n r}{n+1}}^{\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1}} (\|S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])\| + \|u\|) dx \leq \frac{2b_n \|u\|}{n+1}$$

and we can write the above inequality as:

$$\int_{\frac{b_n r}{n+1}}^{\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1}} |S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) - u(x)| dx \leq \frac{b_n}{n+1} \left| u_1\left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1}\right) - u_1(b_n) \right| + \frac{b_n}{n+1} \left| u_2\left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1}\right) - u_2(b_n) \right| + \frac{2b_n \|u\|}{n+1}$$

Now, let us characterize two cases for any $r \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$, as below:

Case (i) Let $x \in \left[\frac{b_n r}{n+1}, \frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1}\right]$ such that $S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) = u_{r, n, r}(x)$

Since, $u_{r, n, r}(x) = u\left(\frac{b_n r}{n}\right) = u_1\left(\frac{b_n r}{n}\right) - u_2\left(\frac{b_n r}{n}\right)$ and by the monotonicity of u_1 and u_2 we get that:

$$|S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) - u(x)| \leq \left| u_1 \left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1} \right) - u_1 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) \right| + \left| u_2 \left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1} \right) - u_2 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) \right|$$

Case (ii) Let $x \in \left[\frac{b_n r}{n+1}, \frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right]$ such that $S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) = u_{r+1, n, r}(x)$, then we have two subcases:

(ii)_a $S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) \leq u(x)$, then $u_{r, n, r}(x) \leq u_{r+1, n, r}(x) \leq u(x)$ so we have:

$$|S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) - u(x)| \leq \left| u_1 \left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1} \right) - u_1 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) \right| + \left| u_2 \left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1} \right) - u_2 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) \right|$$

(ii)_b $S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) > u(x)$, when

$$|S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) - u(x)| \leq \left| u_1 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) - u_1(x) \right| + \left| u_2 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) - u_2(x) \right| \leq \left| u_1 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) - u_1 \left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1} \right) \right| + \left| u_1 \left(\frac{b_n(r+2)}{n+1} \right) - u_1 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) \right| + \left| u_2 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) - u_2 \left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1} \right) \right| + \left| u_2 \left(\frac{b_n(r+2)}{n+1} \right) - u_2 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) \right|$$

Then, we obtain the following when we integrate this inequality on $\left[\frac{b_n r}{n+1}, \frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right]$,

$$\int_{\frac{b_n r}{n+1}}^{\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1}} |S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) - u(x)| dx \leq \frac{b_n}{n+1} \left[\left| u_1 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) - u_1 \left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1} \right) \right| + \left| u_1 \left(\frac{b_n(r+2)}{n+1} \right) - u_1 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) \right| + \left| u_2 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) - u_2 \left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1} \right) \right| + \left| u_2 \left(\frac{b_n(r+2)}{n+1} \right) - u_2 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) \right| \right]$$

Therefore, the following is obtained by summing r from 0 to $n-1$:

$$\int_0^{\frac{b_n n}{n+1}} |S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) - u(x)| dx \leq \frac{b_n}{n+1} \cdot \sum_{r=0}^{n-1} \left| u_1 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) - u_1 \left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1} \right) \right| + \frac{b_n}{n+1} \cdot \sum_{r=0}^{n-1} \left| u_2 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) - u_2 \left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1} \right) \right| + \frac{b_n}{n+1} \cdot \sum_{r=1}^n \left| u_1 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) - u_1 \left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1} \right) \right| + \frac{b_n}{n+1} \cdot \sum_{r=1}^n \left| u_2 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) - u_2 \left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1} \right) \right|$$

And taking the inequality obtained when we started to prove this theorem, we obtain:

$$\int_0^{b_n} |S_n^{(M)}(u; [0, b_n])(x) - u(x)| dx \leq \frac{2b_n}{n+1} \cdot \sum_{r=0}^n \left| u_1 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) - u_1 \left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1} \right) \right|$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{2b_n}{n+1} \cdot \sum_{r=0}^n \left| u_2 \left(\frac{b_n(r+1)}{n+1} \right) - u_2 \left(\frac{b_n r}{n+1} \right) \right| + \frac{2b_n \|u\|}{n+1} \\
 & = \frac{2b_n}{n+1} V_0^{b_n}(u_1) + \frac{2b_n}{n+1} V_0^{b_n}(u_2) + \frac{2b_n \|u\|}{n+1} \\
 & = \frac{2b_n}{n+1} [V_0^{b_n}(u_1) + V_0^{b_n}(u_2) + \|u\|]
 \end{aligned}$$

And by taking $M = 2b_n[V_0^{b_n}(u_1) + V_0^{b_n}(u_2) + \|u\|]$, we can say that the proof of (Case I) is completed.

To prove (Case II), by the same way to prove (Case I)

Hence, we can say this proof is finished. \square

And by extending the results obtained in L^1 -norm to arbitrary compact interval $[a_n, b_n]$, then we can apply it to the approximation of fuzzy numbers, as follows:

By conclusion of Lemma 4.1 we have:

$$\bigvee_{k=0}^n \varphi_{n,k}(x) = \varphi_{n,r}(x), x \in \left[a_n + \frac{(b_n - a_n)r}{n+1}, a_n + \frac{(b_n - a_n)(r+1)}{n+1} \right].$$

Therefore, for $u_{k,n,r}: \left[a_n + \frac{(b_n - a_n)r}{n+1}, a_n + \frac{(b_n - a_n)(r+1)}{n+1} \right] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$,

We can say for each $k, r \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n\}$, we have:

$$u_{k,n,r}(x) = m_{k,n,r}(x) \cdot u \left(a_n + \frac{(b_n - a_n)k}{n} \right)$$

$$\text{Then, } u_{k,n,r}(x) = \binom{n}{k} \cdot \left(\frac{x - a_n}{b_n - a_n} \right)^{k-r} \cdot u \left(a_n + \frac{(b_n - a_n)k}{n} \right)$$

As a result of the above, we can show the following:

Theorem 4.8. Let u be a bounded variation function on $[a_n, b_n]$, such that $\frac{u(x)}{x - a_n}$ is non-increasing on $(a_n, b_n]$ and $\frac{u(x)}{b_n - x}$ is non-decreasing on $[a_n, b_n)$. Then there is $M > 0$ that only depends on u , such that:

$$\int_{a_n}^{b_n} |S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x) - u(x)| dx \leq \frac{M}{n+1}, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Proof. By Remark 3.1, we have $v(y) = u \left(a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{y}{b_n} \right), y \in [0, b_n]$

Let $\frac{y}{b_n} = \frac{x - a_n}{b_n - a_n}$, so we can say $v \left(\frac{b_n(x - a_n)}{b_n - a_n} \right) = u(x)$ and

$x = a_n + (b_n - a_n) \frac{y}{b_n}$, for all $x \in [a_n, b_n]$. Then we have:

$$|S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x) - u(x)| = |S_n^{(M)}(v; [0, b_n])(y) - v(y)|$$

Then, we can easily get:

$$\int_{a_n}^{b_n} |S_n^{(M)}(u; [a_n, b_n])(x) - u(x)| dx = \frac{b_n - a_n}{b_n} \int_0^{b_n} |S_n^{(M)}(v; [0, b_n])(y) - v(y)| dy$$

$$\text{Now, if } \xi(y) = \frac{v(y)}{y} = \frac{u \left(a_n + \frac{(b_n - a_n) \frac{b_n(x - a_n)}{b_n - a_n}}{b_n} \right)}{\frac{b_n(x - a_n)}{b_n - a_n}} = \frac{b_n - a_n}{b_n} \left(\frac{u(x)}{x - a_n} \right)$$

And

$$\rho(y) = \frac{v(y)}{b_n - y} = \frac{u\left(a_n + \frac{(b_n - a_n)b_n(x - a_n)}{b_n - a_n}\right)}{b_n \frac{b_n(x - a_n)}{b_n - a_n}} = \frac{b_n - a_n}{b_n} \left(\frac{u(x)}{b_n - x} \right)$$

Then, directly we can say v satisfies the hypothesis of Theorem 4.7, that is v is of bounded variation on $[0, b_n]$, such that $\xi(y) = \frac{v(y)}{y}$ is non-increasing on $(0, b_n]$ and $\rho(y) = \frac{v(y)}{b_n - y}$ is non-decreasing on $[0, b_n)$.

Hence, we obtain of a constant M_v which only depends on v , such that:

$$\int_0^{b_n} \left| \tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(v; [0, b_n])(y) - v(y) \right| dy \leq \frac{M_v}{n + 1}, n \in \mathbb{N}$$

But because v is a function that depends on u , we can easily determine that M_v only depends on u .

Thus, if we take $M = \frac{b_n - a_n}{b_n} M_v$, we get the intended conclusion. \square

Theorem 4.9. Let $\mu \in \mathbb{R}_F$ such that $\text{supp}(\mu) = [a_n, b_n]$, $\text{core}(\mu) = [c_n, d_n]$, $a_n < c_n \leq d_n < b_n$, and let the restriction of μ to its support $[a_n, b_n]$ fulfills the hypotheses of Theorem 4.8, then we have:

$$D_1 \left(\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n]), \mu \right) \leq \frac{6(b_n - a_n)}{n + 1}, n \in \mathbb{N}$$

Proof. Since $D_1 \left(\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n]), \mu \right) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} \left| \tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x) - \mu(x) \right| dx$,

So, we prove this theorem with the same idea as proving the previous Theorem 4.8.

Therefore, we define the $\xi \in \mathbb{R}_F$, where $\xi(x) = \mu\left(a_n + (b_n - a_n)\frac{x}{b_n}\right)$, if $x \in [0, b_n]$ and $\xi(x) = 0$ if $x \notin [0, b_n]$ that is $\text{supp}(\xi) = [0, b_n]$.

Hence, we deal with ξ by the same steps that were dealt with v in the previous Theorem 4.8, so we get:

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}} \left| \tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x) - \mu(x) \right| dx \leq \frac{b_n - a_n M_\xi}{n + 1}$$

Where the hypothesis of Theorem 4.7 is fulfilled by the restriction of ξ to its support, we are able to take

$$M_\xi = 2b_n[V_0^{b_n}(\xi_1) + V_0^{b_n}(\xi_2) + \|\xi\|]$$

Now we apply the definition of μ_1 and μ_2 in Lemma 4.6 to ξ_1 and ξ_2 in the same way, then easily we get:

$$V_0^{b_n}(\xi_1) = V_0^{b_n}(\xi_2) = 1, \text{ and we know the } \|\xi\| = 1, \text{ we obtain the } M_\xi = 6b_n.$$

This finishes the proof. \square

Remark 4.3. It is worth noting here, that using L^1 -type metrics for fuzzy number approximation by max-product operators offers multiple benefits. These metrics provide efficient computations, clear geometric interpretation, and robustness to outliers. They also enhance the interpretability and efficacy of fuzzy number approximation techniques, making them valuable in various fuzzy logic applications.

Finally, to clarify all the theoretical conclusions mentioned in this paper, we give the following example:

Example 4.1. Let us consider $a_n = \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n$, $b_n = n^{\frac{1}{5}}$. Then approximation of a fuzzy number $\mu(x)$ was illustrated using both the $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ operators and classical operators in (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3), where

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 8x^3 & \text{if } 0 \leq x < \frac{1}{2} \\ 1 & \text{if } \frac{1}{2} \leq x \leq \frac{4}{5} \\ 5 - 5x & \text{if } \frac{4}{5} < x \leq 1 \end{cases}$$

In Fig.2 and Fig.3. It's clear to us that the max-product Bernstein-Chlodowsky operators marked with dashed lines are approximations far better than the (classical) Bernstein-Chlodowsky operators marked with dotted lines. Furthermore, our analysis leads us to the conclusion that as the degree of 'n' increases, the level of approximation by these operators improves significantly.

Figure 2. Approximations by classical and the max- product Bernstein-Chlodowsky operators, n = 20.

Figure 3. Approximations by classical and the max- product Bernstein-Chlodowsky operators, n = 60.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates the significant potential of utilizing the max-product Bernstein-Chlodowsky operators as valuable instruments for approximating fuzzy numbers. Our findings indicate that these operators proficiently preserve both the support and, to a substantial extent, the core of the approximated fuzzy number. From this approximation, several noteworthy conclusions can be drawn:

- (1) The uniform convergence of $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ for the fuzzy number $\mu \in \mathbb{R}_F$ was established when the $\mu_\mu(x)$ is continuous.
- (2) $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x)$ successfully preserves the monotony and shape properties of the approximate $\mu \in \mathbb{R}_F$.
- (3) Improved estimates of convergence, in relation to metrics spaces D_C and L^1 -type, were obtained through the utilization of $\tilde{S}_n^{(M)}(\mu; [a_n, b_n])(x)$.

Acknowledgements: The authors extend their sincere thanks and appreciation to the reviewers for their valuable comments and for reading the manuscript carefully, which will undoubtedly make this work more beautiful and complete.

Data availability: The data used in this work are included in the manuscript.

Conflicts of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding statement: This work doesn't have any funding or support.

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8358833](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8358833)